

Technical Report

wAlter: Serving Awareness* — Environmental Footprint Estimator for Artificial Intelligence Models[†]

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1. Introduction

The rapid growth of Artificial Intelligence (AI) usage in recent years has driven advances in several fields of study, such as healthcare, technology in general, and even supporting on the combat of climate change. Developments in the area of Deep Learning, with models for image, text, and voice recognition, are becoming increasingly popular. However, these models have also grown larger each year, both in terms of the data required for training and the number of parameters to be tuned (reaching the order of trillions in the case of GPT-4, used by ChatGPT). The idea that adding more data and parameters to a model leads to better results, even if only by small margins, that is, the paradigm of “more is better”, has brought consequences regarding the energy consumption required for training these models and, consequently, the emission of carbon dioxide (CO₂) and water consumption.

Studies have shown that preparing a complete pipeline for the development of large AI models can emit as much carbon as five cars throughout their entire lifetime [Strubell et al. 2019], and that every 50 questions and answers from ChatGPT may consume the equivalent of a 500 ml bottle of water [Li et al. 2025]. To study this impact, methods have been proposed to estimate the energy consumption of the application/model, as well as its water and carbon footprint [Ferro et al. 2023, Yokoyama et al. 2023].

In datacenters or individual computers, energy is used to keep all systems operational, which encompasses hardware like CPUs and GPUs, as well as cooling systems. To measure the energy usage of running an AI model or any software, external power meters or built-in computer sensors can be employed. External meters tend to be more precise in general but are difficult and expensive to have. On the other hand, internal sensors are readily available, though less accurate. The energy consumption of system components such as the processor (CPU), graphics card (GPU), and RAM is estimated using a factor called Thermal Design Power (TDP), which is given in watts (W) and described in the component’s specifications.

It is worthy of noticing that computers do not emit CO₂ or consume water directly. However, the amount of energy consumed is the basis to estimate the carbon and water

*João Pedro Santos de Rezende was who named the calculator.

[†]*Beta version*

footprints associated. In addition to the hardware used to launch the AI model, the carbon and water footprint estimation should consider the complete infrastructure that constitutes the environment of the machine. It represents the energy needed to support the entire computing infrastructure. Considering those, in the metrics, it is possible to evaluate the energy efficiency of data centers.

Electricity consumption is one responsible for the Greenhouse Gas Emissions (GHG), among which carbon dioxide (CO₂) is the most significant. Despite the fact that computers do not emit CO₂, it is possible to estimate the amount of CO₂ equivalent (CO₂e) linked to the execution of algorithms in computing environments. This conversion into CO₂e considers the relative proportions of the different energy sources, such as hydroelectric and coal plants. In [Patterson et al. 2021] the authors updated the results of [Strubell et al. 2019] and pointed to a reduction of the GHG emission by a factor of 100 if one considers the location of the data center used for training. [Luccioni et al. 2020, Patterson et al. 2021, Yokoyama et al. 2023] found that emissions can vary by up to a factor of depending on the energy source of the grid.

However, performing this type of calculation and accessing the values of these constants and variables is not a trivial task. This hinders awareness and transparency regarding the training of these models.

Due to the complexities of collecting energy and carbon metrics, several tools have been proposed to make more visible the impacts of training models [Breder et al. 2024]. Experiment Impact Tracker ¹, Carbon Tracker ² and CodeCarbon ³ are Python packages reporting measured energy and the associated carbon footprint. Also, there are online tools, such as Green Algorithms ⁴ and MLCO₂ impact [Luccioni et al. 2020], which can be less accurate but easier to use. In [Breder et al. 2024] we evaluated some of these tools and discussed their advantages and limitations.

How is the water footprint estimated, and what role does AI play in water usage? Water consumption occurs in three primary ways: through cooling systems to manage server temperatures, in electricity production to power the system, and within the supply chain during server manufacturing [Li et al. 2025]. As of now, we lack any tools comparable to those for carbon estimation that can help with assessing this footprint.

So, the main motivation for creating a new tool for calculating the environmental footprint is that these web tools currently do not estimate the water footprint of AI models; their focus is exclusively on the carbon. Furthermore, our tool also allows estimating the carbon and water footprint, even when the user already knows the amount of energy consumed for a task (running, training, or inferring a model), using, for example, external power meters. Thus, the tool addresses the three costs of training an AI model: energy consumption, CO₂e emissions, and water footprint. In addition, it presents comparisons with other sources of energy consumption and CO₂ emissions common in our activities, such as light bulbs and cars.

Therefore, this report aims to detail the creation and functionality of the **wAIter**

¹<https://github.com/Breakend/experiment-impact-tracker>

²<https://github.com/lfwa/carbontracker>

³<https://codecarbon.io/>

⁴<http://www.green-algorithms.org/>

tool, which enables researchers and developers to assess energy usage. From this assessment, they can determine the carbon emissions released into the atmosphere and the water consumption involved in executing or training an AI model [Shehabi et al. 2016].

2. Methodology

To estimate the amount of energy consumed, this work was based on the studies [Ferro et al. 2023, Yokoyama et al. 2023, Strubell et al. 2019], which present an equation designed to estimate the amount of energy consumed by a server over a given time, as well as the amount of carbon equivalent emitted by it. Furthermore, totally based on the study of [Li et al. 2023], it was possible to estimate the amount of water consumed according to the previously calculated energy.

Several factors are necessary to calculate the carbon emissions associated with a system's energy consumption. A primary factor is the country where the systems are installed, due to its associated energy grid. National energy production is divided into low-carbon and high-carbon sources. Low-carbon sources include renewable — such as hydroelectric, wind, and solar — as well as nuclear power. High-carbon sources, on the other hand, consist of fossil fuels like coal, oil, and natural gas. Consequently, the calculation of the equivalent carbon emissions for an AI model is directly related to the country where the model was trained. A country with an energy grid composed mostly of low-carbon sources will have a lower carbon intensity factor than a country reliant primarily on high-carbon sources.

Furthermore, internal system factors must be considered, defined as **Power Usage Effectiveness** (PUE) and **Water Usage Effectiveness** (WUE). PUE relates to energy consumption, while WUE relates to water consumption.

PUE is calculated as the ratio of the total energy consumed by a datacenter to the amount used solely to power IT equipment. This metric accounts for energy used by supporting infrastructure, such as cooling and lighting systems.

WUE is subdivided into two categories: internal WUE and external WUE [Li et al. 2025]. Internal WUE refers to all water evaporated on-site within the system where the AI training or inference takes place. External WUE (off-site) refers to all water evaporated during the production of the electricity used by the system; it is therefore related to the energy grid of the country. Different power generation sources consume varying amounts of water per kWh generated.

In our tool, the energy and carbon footprint estimation followed Equations 1 and 2.

First, the Equation 1 is used for energy estimation (kWh), where:

- e represents the power consumed, in watts;
- t the time the application spent running, in seconds;
- θ is the server PUE. Power Usage Effectiveness formula is: $PUE = \text{Total Energy Used by Facility} / \text{Energy Used by IT Equipment}$. A lower PUE value indicates greater energy efficiency, with a value of 1 representing perfect efficiency, where all energy goes directly to the IT equipment and none is wasted on infrastructure like cooling or lighting ⁵.

⁵<https://www.nlyte.com/blog/data-center-energy-efficiency-pue-dcie/>

- p_c, p_r, p_g are the power consumed by the CPU, RAM, and GPU components, respectively.

Based on this, the calculation of carbon equivalent emissions CO_2e is carried out by multiplying the system power e consumed over time t by the country’s carbon intensity c_i , as shown in Equation 2.

$$e = \frac{\theta \cdot t(p_c + p_r + g \cdot p_g)}{1000} \quad (1)$$

$$CO_2e = c_i \cdot e \quad (2)$$

For calculating the water footprint (w) of AI models, Equation 3 was used, where e the energy consumed in watts, calculated using Eq. 1; ρ_{s1}, ρ_{s2} the on-site and off-site WUE, respectively; and finally, θ the server PUE.

$$w = e \cdot [\rho_{s1} + \theta \cdot \rho_{s2}] \quad (3)$$

The carbon intensity c_i for each country was sourced from the dataset provided by [Ember et al. 2025], while the off-site WUE variable ρ_{s2} for each nation was derived from the findings of [Reig et al. 2020]. The TDP for both CPUs and GPUs was gathered manually from the *websites* TechPowerUP.

3. wAIter Tool

The initial prototype (beta version) of the **wAIter - Serving Awareness** calculator was created using details about the machine’s components and the country where the AI training or inference took place, as described in the previous section.

This version enables users to estimate the energy usage, the carbon emissions released into the atmosphere, and the volume of water consumed. **wAIter** is composed of the following fields:

- Time (*Time* (s)) – time spent in seconds (s) on the AI model training
- CPU – processor model used
- GPU – graphics card model used
- On-site WUE – internal water-use efficiency of the server employed for model training
- Country – country of the server used for training
- PUE – internal power usage effectiveness of the server.
- “Calculate” button – returns to the user the energy consumed, carbon footprint, and water footprint

Figure 1 illustrates the input fields of the calculator, where the user can provide information such as training time, *hardware* specifications, server country, as well as the server’s internal WUE and PUE. If the total energy consumption is already known, the user may input this value directly.

For using the calculator, the user must enter the training duration of the AI model in seconds in the Time field. In the CPU and GPU fields, the user specifies the machine’s

hardware where the model was trained. In the Country field, the user indicates the location of the model training. Finally, in the on-site WUE and PUE fields, the user must provide the water and energy efficiency of the server where the training was carried out. If the training was conducted on a regular machine or if no information is available regarding WUE or PUE, the default values used are 0 and 1, respectively.

Figure 1. Input section - wAlter.

Based on the provided inputs, the calculator generates an output (Figure 2) with the estimated energy consumption, CO₂ emissions, and water usage. In addition, the system presents comparative metrics, such as the equivalent hours of a light bulb (60W) turned on, the kilometers driven by an average car in Brazil (0.096 kg/CO₂)⁶, and the number of 500 ml water bottles.

Figure 2. Output section - wAlter.

The calculator is available at: <https://rionowcast-green.github.io/walter-calculator/>.

⁶<https://www.terra.com.br/mobilidade/carros/10-carros-mais-vendidos-do-brasil-juntos-emitem-toneladas-de-co2km,94edb86d5539c509875a33d4f89be399qaatriqn.html>

3.1. Examples of Results

One small-scale example of the wAlter usage is the result obtained from our work that can be found at the "Anais do Eniac 2025 - Beyond Accuracy: A Comparative Study of Machine Learning Models for Extreme Weather Forecasting in Rio de Janeiro with a Green AI Perspective", when for the training and tuning of the ML models, we consumed 0.0263 kWh of energy, which corresponds to 30 minutes of use of a light bulb of 60 W, 0.0025 kg CO₂e emissions, and 0.4888 liters of water.

Figure 3. Output TikTok example using wAlter.

An extensive example involved evaluating the impact of the TikTok data center planned for Caucaia-CE, Brazil. As reported by Intercept ⁷, the data center's power capacity is 210 MW, resulting in a daily consumption of 5040 MWh (24 hours multiplied by 210 MW), which translates to over 5 million kWh within a single day. When analyzed with wAlter, these numbers are substantial (Figure 3): approximately 495,000 kg of CO₂e emissions per day, requiring more than 13 million trees for carbon offsetting. Additionally, the water usage surpasses 93 million liters, akin to the volume of 37 Olympic-sized swimming pools.

4. Final Considerations

This is the first version of the calculator, and its primary purpose is to facilitate the estimation of energy consumption and equivalent environmental impacts. We believe these results help raise awareness about these environmental impacts and encourage the scientific community to seek solutions—for example, by choosing more modest and sustainable models and demanding transparency from developers regarding their models.

In future versions, the use of .csv files will be available to streamline various calculations from experiments, as well as a version for high-performance environments involving distributed and parallel computing experiments. Also, we are working to improve the precision of the estimations, especially in regard to the energy calculations.

Ethical Declaration: We used the Writefull tool, a large language model based on GPT, integrated with Overleaf to assist in the grammatical correction and improvement

⁷<https://www.intercept.com.br/2025/07/24/descubra-quem-gasta-mais-energia-data-center-tikiok-ou-a-sua-cidade/>

suggestions of this text. Each AI suggestion was made based on our own text and was carefully reviewed, which makes us fully responsible for the form and content of the text of this work.

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